

St. Nicholas of Melissourgoi

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St. Nicholas is the main church of the village Melissourgoi of Arta in Greece. The church was originally built in the second half of the 18th century. It was burnt by the Ottomans in 1821 and by Nazi troops in WWII.

Date Range: 1778 CE - 1967 CE

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Region tags: Greece

A mountainous area in the Pindos mountains, named Voulgareli.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Makris, Kitsos. Χιονιαδίτες Ζωγράφοι 65 λαϊκοί ζωγράφοι από το χωριό Χιονιάδες της Ηπείρου. Athens, Greece: Melissa Publications, 1981.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.imartis.gr/πολιτισμός/ιστορία-μνημεία/μεταβυζαντινά-μνημεία/64-ο-ναός-του-αγίου-νικολάου-στους-μελισσουργούς.html>

– Source 1 Description: Official description of the monument by the Metropolis of Arta.

– Source 2 URL:

https://www.greece.com/photos/destinations/Epirus/Arta/Town/Melissourgi/Άγιος_Νικόλαος_καμπαναριό_Μελισσουργοι

– Source 2 Description: The bell tower of the church.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

- Rock face

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

↳ Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Clearing
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Notes: The village of Melissourgoi, Arta.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

↳ A single structure

- No

↳ One single feature

- Mound

↳ A group of structures:

- Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes
- ↳ A group of features:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Other [specify]: Both communal and individual.
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Burned

Notes: Twice due to war and a revolution.
 - ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - For religious reasons
 - For political reasons
 - As the result of war
 - ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Other [specify]: Damaged by earthquake.
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - Periodically

- ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Saint Nicholas

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Holy Trinity

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: But it commemorates them.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

- ↳ Groups:
 - Priests
 - Men
 - Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 90

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Cement added later

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Cement

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:
A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted
– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Yes

↳ Floral motifs
– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: Post-byzantine Frescoes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Angels

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: As a part of the wooden altar

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Wooden parts of the throne of the bishop and the altarpiece.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: By the famous Chioniadites painters.

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Alexander the Great and Darius are depicted in Hell.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions are present almost on every part of the interior.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Textiles

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Various themes including Greek history.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: It commemorates the dead ritually.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– I don't know

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
–Other [specify]: Holy Trinity

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

- ↳ In dreams:
 - No
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Divine Liturgy

Are previously human spirits present:
– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:
– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

–Yes [specify]: Olive oil

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: Bread (Prosphora)

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Through prayer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: Oaths taken within the site.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Through prayer.
- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: 5
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Monthly
 - Notes: A few years back, daily.
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - No

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No

- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

– Yes

Notes: Bloodless ritual sacrifices in the Divine Liturgy.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - No

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - Yes

Notes: For candles.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Metal oblations under icons can be observed.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: By members of the ecclesiastical committee, which is consisted by members of the local community.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The initial cleansing of the site was conducted by priests and involved relics.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Local community

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

- ↳ Cleansing
 - Yes
- ↳ Offerings of models of body parts:
 - Yes
- ↳ Expiation
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: All through the participation in the rituals.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - No
- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Metropolis of Arta

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

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- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - No

- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - No

- ↳ Function for water management:
 - No

- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Religious ceremonies take place, such as baptisms and marriages.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: St. Nicholas of Melissourgoi, Makris, Kitsos. Χιονιάδιτες ζωγράφοι 65 λαϊκοί ζωγράφοι από το χωριό χιονιάδες της ηπείρου. Athens, Greece: Melissa Publications, 1981.